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ENERGY-EFFICIENT MODERN BUILDING MATERIALS IN CONSTRUCTION

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Annotation: This article talks about energy efficiency, energy-saving insulation materials, modern building materials and their rational use. The article also reflects the importance of energy efficiency in construction

Key words: energy efficiency, energy resources, insulating material, heat insulator, transparent structures, energy-saving materials

Energy efficiency means rational use of energy. Energy saving potential is very important for the whole world and Karakalpakstan in particular.

About 40% of the energy consumed in the world is used in buildings. They are the main consumers of energy and the main sources of greenhouse gas emissions. 2/3 of this energy is spent on heating and air cleaning, and modern technologies can significantly reduce this figure.

Modern trends and perspectives of construction and reconstruction of buildings are primarily related to a rational approach to the use of energy resources, a comfortable indoor climate and reducing the impact on the environment.

The main result of the increased requirements for thermal protection of building envelopes was the transition to multi-layer structural solutions. They allow to achieve high resistance to heat transfer without increasing the thickness of the surrounding structures due to the effect of effective heaters.

Various heat-insulating materials and constructions, energy-saving facade systems, solid-form monolithic house building technologies and energy-saving transparent structures are used in the construction.

The most effective heat insulator in construction is air. The main difference between the heat-saving properties of building materials is the ratio of the volume of air spaces to the volume of the frame skeleton that forms these holes. At the same time, a characteristic relationship is observed between the material's thermal conductivity, specific gravity, and its strength properties. In addition, air can be an independent layer of insulation in multi-layer walls.

Materials with significant heat protection properties are a priority in the construction market.

The heat-efficient building block made of silicon granite is made of a building material with high energy-saving qualities and durability. This block is a layered cake, in which the first layer is responsible for the bearing capacity of the wall, the next one is effective insulation, the next layer is a support layer and performs several functions at the same time:

- works well for insulation;
- meets the load-bearing capacity of the wall;
- serves as the basis for the outer finishing layer.
- And the last layer - various decorative coatings.

Heat-efficient building block. Reducing the consumption of fuel and energy resources is especially important when using brick buildings. The conducted experiments made it possible to develop the main directions for achieving a high level of heat protection quality without increasing the thickness of external brick walls. World construction practice shows that the construction of exterior walls from facing bricks and large-format ceramic blocks are the most advanced technical and energy-saving solutions. This ensures high rates of strength and stability of buildings, as well as a high level of heat conservation. In this case, not only the optimal temperature-humidity and hygienic conditions inside the buildings, but also the mode of air exchange inside the walls are created. The quality indicators of porous bricks are related to their structure with many microscopic air spaces, which provide the brick with excellent thermal insulation properties.

The following are most often used as heat insulators in facade design solutions:

- heat-insulating plates from mineral wool;
- extruded polyethylene foam;
- heat insulating plates made of basalt rocks;
- foam glass plates (blocks), etc.

Heat losses through windows reach up to 50% of total heat losses through building envelopes. Therefore, the most important task of energy saving in buildings is to improve the thermal protection properties of transparent closed structures, first of all, windows.

The modern building materials industry produces a variety of energy-efficient windows:

Energy-saving glass has a number of advantages:

- reflects long-wave heat rays to its emitter (in winter to an apartment with heating devices, and in summer to a street with solar-heated stones, asphalt, etc.), which reduces costs. heating in winter and air conditioning in summer;

- has high heat insulation ability;
- reduces the possibility of condensation on the glass, because the temperature on the surface of double-glazed glass is higher than on the surface of ordinary glass;
- prevents tarnishing of floor coverings and interior items.

The operational energy efficiency of buildings is primarily shaped by its thermal and energy efficiency, which in turn depends on the thermal protection properties of the transparent parts of the outer shell of the building.

Increasing the energy efficiency of buildings can only be achieved through the use of integrated architectural and construction solutions.

The design potential of energy saving in buildings and structures largely depends on the experience and qualifications of the project authors, the real potential depends on the quality of construction works and the correctness of project decisions at the construction stage.

The market of energy-efficient building materials is very wide, but their selection should be based on thermal engineering calculations and design and planning solutions for energy saving in buildings.

The use of modern energy-efficient structures and materials makes it possible to create buildings not only with low energy consumption, but also with various indicators of the price range, comfort and environmental friendliness, which is certainly relevant in the modern construction industry.

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